

Optimism, Emotional Intelligence and Psychological Distress First-Borns in Early Adulthood

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to examine whether optimism and emotional intelligence affect psychological distress in early adulthood with first birth order or firstborns. The participants in this study totaled 100 early adult males and females with the order of first birth or firstborn. The research design is cross-sectional and non-experimental. The measuring instrument used in the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10) study is to measure psychological distress, the Emotional Intelligence Scale Developed is to measure emotional intelligence, the Life Orientation Test-Revised (LOT-R) is to measure optimism. The analysis technique in this study used multiple regression tests. The results of this study indicate that there is no contribution of optimism and emotional intelligence to psychological distress in early adult firstborns.

Keywords: *Optimism, Emotional Intelligence, Psychological Distress, Early Adulthood, Young Adults, Firstling, Firstborn Child.*

INTRODUCTION

The population of Indonesia has always increased every year, which makes Indonesia's population more and more. According to data from the Central Bureau of Statistics (2021) in 2020 the population of Indonesia amounted to around 270 million people. In 2021, it has increased with a total population of 272 million. The data includes data on the age of children 0-9 years with a percentage of the population with a child age of 16.16%, adolescence age 16.27%, middle adulthood 21.50%, late adulthood 6.43% and early adulthood age with the highest percentage of 39.64%. Early adulthood is the largest population in Indonesia with 108 million people.

According to Hurlock (in Putri, 2019) an early adult is someone who has an age range of around 18 - 40 years. However, in general, early adulthood is categorized as starting at the age of 20-40 years. The early adult developmental period is very important for a person's developmental phase because early adult individuals are in the reproductive phase which has various demands in the form of developmental tasks that must be fulfilled, such as working, choosing a partner, building a family, caring for children, managing a household, taking responsibility as a citizen, and joining social groups (Hurlock, 2004). The impact of shifting demands, roles, and responsibilities is illustrated by five characteristics possessed by early adulthood including *identity exploration*, *instability*, *self-focus*, *feeling in between*, and *optimism* (Reifman, Arnett, & Colwell, 2007). Judging from these characteristics, early adulthood has optimism but is more dominated by experiencing instability.

First-born children are often referred to as *experimental* children, due to the lack of knowledge

and experience of parents in raising children will have an effect on him. As a result, parents tend to be anxious and overprotective and do not fully understand their role as parents (Gunarsa, 1995). Firstborn children occupy a unique position, where the firstborn child experiences a transition in position that starts as a single child for some time and then becomes an older sibling when a younger sibling is born. This event changes the situation and the way the firstborn child views the world. Adler (in Feist & Feist, 2013) revealed that firstborns tend to have positive traits, namely caring for and protecting others and being good organizers, but firstborns also have negative traits, namely having high anxiety, being too independent, having excessive feelings of power, unconscious hostility, struggling for recognition, having to be "right" while others are always "wrong", strongly criticizing others and not being able to cooperate (Feist & Feist, 2013).

Early adults with the first birth order or firstborn are in a transitional phase. With new demands that must be faced with a sense of optimism but have instability and high responsibility. Like the research conducted by Wahid and Ridfah (2017) that children Firstborns have a sense of responsibility with a medium to high category. The sense of responsibility that firstborn children have in the early adult phase sometimes causes anxiety and depression. In the field of psychology, anxiety and depression are dimensions of *psychological distress*. *Psychological distress* is an unpleasant emotional state and is usually indicated by symptoms of anxiety (for example, lack of rest, tension) and depression (loss of interest, sadness, lack of hope) (Mirowsky & Ross, 2002).

There are various factors that can affect *psychological distress* in individuals, including optimism. Optimism is how when someone is positive about a situation. Optimistic individuals will make efforts to overcome unfavourable circumstances for themselves, think that bad circumstances are a challenge, do not feel hopeless quickly, and have social support and ultimately individuals will have better health (Seligman, 2005). There are several aspects of an individual's view of an event or problem that are closely related to the *explanatory style*, namely: *permanence*, *pervasive* (*Universal-Specific*), and *personalization*.

With the many demands and responsibilities that first children have, this can cause *distress*. Distress is stress that has a harmful effect on the individual experiencing it, such as unpleasant or excessive demands that drain individual energy, making it easier to fall ill (Dewi, 2012). With this, in dealing with the demands and challenges that firstborns have in early adulthood, therefore optimism can be an important factor. Therefore, optimism can provide meaning in *psychological distress*, namely anxiety and depression in facing the demands and challenges of life for firstborns in early adulthood (Tanjung, Huriyani & Rahman, 2021).

Based on the results of previous research conducted by Hutapea and Mashoedi (2019), there is a negative relationship between optimism and *psychological distress* in high school students. Which means that if an individual has a high level of optimism, the individual has a low level of *psychological distress* and vice-versa.

Psychological distress experienced by individuals is not only influenced by optimism but can also be influenced by *emotional intelligence*. *Emotional intelligence* is the ability to understand, access and generate emotions so that they can help in thinking, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to regulate emotions so that they can encourage emotional and intellectual growth (Salovey & John D. Mayer, 1990).

The abundant demands and challenges experienced by early adult firstborns require the ability

to understand and regulate their emotions well, so that they can control their anxiety and depression well. Based on the results of previous research conducted by Jamaludin and Dewi (2016), there is an influence of *emotional intelligence* with a negative direction on *psychological distress* in adolescents. It can be interpreted that if an individual has a high level of *emotional intelligence*, the individual has a lower level of *psychological distress*.

Research related to *optimism* and *emotional intelligence* with *psychological distress* was previously only conducted in adolescence. In the early adult development period with the transition of demands for new roles and responsibilities, early adults must be faster in adapting to these changes. Early adults who The role of the firstborn also has additional responsibilities because they have to be an example for their younger siblings and sometimes have to help with family financial problems or become the backbone of the family to replace the role of parents. Based on the reasons and theoretical arguments previously described, the hypothesis of this study is that there is an influence between optimism and *emotional intelligence* with *psychological distress* in early adults with the first birth order or firstborn. This study also tries to explore gender differences in looking at the above variables.

RESEARCH METHODS

The participants of this study involved 100 children with the first order or firstborn with the number of male participants as many as 25 people, and the number of female participants as many as 75 people. The sampling technique was determined using a *non-probability sampling* technique, namely *purposive sampling*. Participants were reached using an online questionnaire. The online questionnaire link was distributed using the *snowball sampling* technique on the researcher's social media account and shared with several relatives of the researcher. The questionnaire contained *informed consent*, participant identity, and a number of scales for each variable. In the introductory section of the online questionnaire, special criteria for participants were mentioned (1) male and female (2) aged 20 to 40 years (3) First birth order or firstborn.

This researcher is a quantitative type research. The research design used is *cross-sectional* and non-experimental. In this study, *psychological distress* was measured using the *Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10)* which was adapted from Kessler (2003). This scale consists of 10 items. An example of this scale is "In the past 4 weeks, approximately how often have you felt nervous?". This scale has response categories ranging from Never at All Times to All the Time with a score range of 1-5. After going through the calculation of item discrimination power, out of 10 items there are no invalid items so that this scale has a reliability value of 0.885.

Optimism is measured using the adapted *Life Orientation Test- Revised (LOT-R)* scale, which was developed by Scheier, Carver, and Bridges (1994) This scale consists of 10 items and there are 4 neutral items that are not included in the calculation. An example of this scale is "I'm always optimistic about my future". This scale has response categories ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree with a score range of 1-5. Of the 6 items that went through the item discrimination power test, there were no invalid items so that this scale had a reliability value of 0.727.

In this study, *emotional intelligence* is measured using the *Emotional Intelligence Scale Developed* scale adapted from Salovey (1990). This scale consists of 33 items. An example of this scale is "I know why my emotions change". This scale has response categories ranging from Strongly

Disagree to Strongly Agree with a score range of 1-5. After going through the item discrimination test, none of the 33 items on this scale were cancel so that the number of items on this scale remained with a reliability value of 0.819. This research uses analytical techniques with multiple linear regression tests with the help of *SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) Version 26.0 for Mac*. Meanwhile, other demographic and descriptive data were presented using percentage calculations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the findings related to demographic data, it can be seen in Table 1. Data exposure in table 1, contains data regarding gender, age of last education, occupation, domicile, relationship status, number of siblings, relationship status of parents and having financial dependents for the family (mother, father, and younger siblings). Based on the explanation in Table 1, it can be seen that the majority of eldest children have financial dependents for their families, whether in a married or unmarried relationship status. In addition, the financial dependents of firstborn children also occur in the relationship of parents who are still married, divorced, or divorced. Being the firstborn child has its own responsibilities and is different among children with other birth orders, as can be seen in the table 1 below. that the biggest responsibilities experienced by eldest children include the responsibility to guide and be an example for younger siblings, the responsibility to be able to follow parents' expectations, the responsibility to help the family *financially*, the responsibility to be a reliable person in the family in all matters, the responsibility to keep family members getting along with each other, and the responsibility to be a substitute for a father figure if the father is gone. With this great responsibility, it can affect the level of *stress* in early adult firstborn children.

Table 1. Description of Demographic and Open Questions

Keterangan	Jumlah	Persentase (%)
Gender		
Male	25	25%
Female	75	75%
Education		
High school	22	22%
Diploma	7	7%
Bachelor	64	64%
Master	7	7%
Age		
18 – 25 years old	74	74%
25 – 32 years old	20	20%
33 – 40 years old	6	6%

Relationship Status		
Single	53	53%
Dating	25	25%
Engaged	5	5%
Married	17	17%
Jobs		
Students	29	29%
Private Employee	44	44%
Civil Servants	10	10%
Entrepreneurship	4	4%
Lecturer or Teacher	9	9%
Health Professionals (Doctors, Nurses, and Psychologists)	4	4%
Domicile		
DKI Jakarta	51	51%
West Java	35	35%
Central Java	3	3%
East Java	3	3%
Banten	6	6%
Bali	2	2%
Number of Siblings		
1	51	51%
2	33	33%
3	14	14%
4	2	2%
Parent Relationship		
Married	78	78%
Divorce	10	10%
Death Divorce	12	12%
Have family financial dependents		
Yes	51	51%
No	49	49%
Biggest Responsibility as The Firstborn		
Guiding and as an example for younger siblings	34	34%
Following parental expectations	23	23%
Assist in family finances	22	22%
Being the go-to person in the family for everything	15	15%
Making sure families get along with each other	3	3%
Being a substitute for a father figure	3	3%

Table 2. Effect of Optimism and Emotional Intelligence on Psychological Distress

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	25.2780	8.313		3.101	.003
Optimism	-.454	.387	-.190	-1.174	.243
Emotional Intelligence	.079	.105	.122	.753	.453

Tabel 3. Regression Test Results Optimism, Emotional Intelligence on Psychological Distress

F	sig.	p	R.Square
.724	.488	> 0.05	.015

In table 2, the significance coefficient value is obtained for the variable Then the coefficient of significance on the *emotional intelligence* variable is 0.453 ($p > 0.05$) with $\beta = 0.122$ or 12.2% of the effect. This shows that both variables do not significantly affect the *psychological distress of children with the first order or firstborn in early adulthood*. Furthermore, in Table 3, the F value is 0.724 and the significance coefficient is 0.488 ($p > 0.05$), this shows that there is no significant influence between *optimism* and *emotional intelligence* on *psychological distress* in first-order children or firstborn children in early adulthood. In addition, an R square value of 0.015 was also obtained, indicating that *optimism* and *emotional intelligence* together influence *psychological distress* by 1.5%. The results of this research indicate that *optimism* and *emotional intelligence* are only minor predictors of *psychological distress* in firstborn children in early adulthood.

This may be due to the distribution of questionnaires that cannot describe the population evenly where it can be seen in table 1, the description of demographic data on the domicile of filling out the questionnaire has an uneven proportion. In addition, another possibility Because the majority of participants who filled out the research questionnaire were women with a total of 75 people, this could affect the results of this study where women use more affection from others or social support as a negative influence on *psychological distress*. This is supported by research conducted by Aliyah and Kusdiyati (2021) regarding *perceived social support* on *psychological distress* in adolescent X during the COVID-19 pandemic where women have a significantly higher influence than men.

In addition, there are other factors that influence *psychological distress* in first- order children in early adulthood. This study is different from previous research, where *optimism* has a significant negative relationship with *psychological distress* in early adults with low or poor economic levels (Hutapea & Mashoedi, 2019). In addition, this study also differs from research on *emotional intelligence* with *stress*, which has a significantly negative relationship in early adults who are in the *quarter life crisis* phase.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, *optimism* and *emotional intelligence*

The effect of emotional *intelligence* on *psychological intelligence* does not have a significant effect on firstborn children who are in early adulthood. *Psychological distress* experienced by firstborn children in early adulthood has other factors that are greater than *emotional intelligence* and *optimism* in facing the challenges and responsibilities they have as firstborn children.

For future researchers, it is recommended to pay attention to other variables that have a greater influence on *psychological distress*. This research has not been measured in this study and can use those that can influence externally because in this study the two variables still use internal variables. Future research can use variables such as parenting, social support, and others. In addition, future researchers are also advised to distribute questionnaires evenly so that they can better represent the existing population and get a balanced number of participants between male and female participants.

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